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**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
BY
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Date: 2023/09/25

WEB BASED CINEMA SEAT ALLOCATION SYSTEM

- CASE STUDY KATHMANDU PLAZA

ABSTRACT

A computer reservation system or central reservation system is a computerized system used to store and retrieve information and conduct transactions related to air travel, hotels, car rental, or activities. These systems typically allow users to book hotel rooms, rental cars, airline tickets as well as activities and tours. They also provide access to railway reservations and bus reservations in some markets, although these are not always integrated with the main system. For these systems to be accessible on mobile phones and computers outside the premises of the airport, cinema, train station or stadiums, they need to be on the internet or a network.

This project focuses on the design and implementation of a web based cinema management system for the allocation of seat tickets online. The system would feature the registration of users, use of serial numbers and pins gotten from scratch cards sold and a printed slip. The system would have a store of all the seats and automate the generation of fresh serial numbers and pins.

CHAPTER ONE- INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

A movie theater or movie theatre (also called a cinema, movie house, film house, film theater or picture house) is a venue, usually a building, for viewing movies (films). Most but not all movie theaters are commercial operations catering to the general public, who attend by purchasing a ticket. The movie is projected with a movie projector onto a large projection screen at the front of the auditorium. Most movie theaters are now equipped for digital cinema projection, removing the need to create and transport a physical film print.

Nigerian film industry had always been making films on celluloid and the films were screened in cinema houses across Nigeria and later released on VHS for various homes. However, the release of the Straight-to-video movie *Living in Bondage* in 1992 by NEK Video Links owned by Kenneth Nnebue launched the Home video market in Nigeria. Nnebue had an excess number of imported video cassettes which he then used to shoot his first film on a Video Camera. Nollywood exploded into a booming industry in the late '90s and pushed foreign media off the shelves. It is now an industry marketed all over Africa and the rest of the world. Thus the use of cinemas has a long history and reveals the general acceptance of cinema use. But the seat reservation and management of movies needs to be computerized.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There is a problem of having online access to the booking system of most cinema viewing centers. Tickets may have to be purchased on site and seat booking is not feasible over the internet.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study is to

- Design and implement a web based cinema management system.
- Test the system online using test data
- Explain the benefits of using computers in information management

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

- a. It would automate the process of booking for cinema seat space online
- b. Generation of pins and serial numbers for cinema cards will be present
- c. Digital format of viewers will be stored
- d. Movies lists can be accessible over the internet

1.5 SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

The scope of this work will include the following

- a. Development of cinema management system to enhance ticket booking and processing online.
- b. Presentation of flowcharts and database design of system

1.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This project is limited to the use of scratch cards in accessing the system as online payment processing is expensive to implement.

1.7 DEFINITION OF TERMS/VARIABLES

- a. **Cinema:** a place designed for the exhibition of films
- b. **Network** - a connection of computer systems using a network media
- c. **System** – Computer software designed to carry out a specific task.
- d. **Web based software/system** – this refers to a software accessible over a network such as the internet or intranet (Local Area Network)

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INFORMATION MANGEMENT SYSTEM

An information management system or management information system (MIS) provides information that is needed to manage organizations efficiently and effectively. Management information systems are not only computer systems - these systems encompass three primary components: technology, people (individuals, groups, or organizations), and data/information for decision making (Dweiri, 2005). Management information systems are distinct from other information systems in that they are designed to be used to analyze and facilitate strategic and operational activities in the organization. Academically, the term is commonly used to refer to the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations evaluate, design, implement, manage, and utilize systems to generate information to improve efficiency and effectiveness of decision making, including systems termed decision support systems, expert systems, and executive information systems. A management information system is also a set of processes that allows companies to move information through their business operations. Business owners and managers use the information to make decisions, among other things. The expanding variety and use of information technology---particularly computers---allows companies to automate this critical business function. (Wikipedia, 2012).

2.1 EFFECTS OF USING COMPUTERIZED INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Companies are able to highlight their strengths and weaknesses due to the presence of revenue reports, employees' performance record etc. The identification of these aspects can help the organization improve their business processes and operations. Giving an overall picture of the organization and acting as a communication and planning tool. The availability of the customer data and feedback can help the organization to align their business processes according to the needs of the customers. The effective management of customer data can help the organization to perform direct marketing and promotion activities. Information is considered to be an important asset for any organization in the modern competitive world. The consumer buying trends and behaviours can be predicted by the analysis of sales and revenue reports from each operating region of the organization. (Dweiri, 2005)

Management information systems have changed the dynamics of running businesses efficiently. Decentralization is one of the biggest advantages; it allows monitoring of operations at low levels and frees up resources for departmental managers to devote time to strategic activities. Coordination of specialized projects and activities is much better and decision makers in the organization are aware of issues and problems in all departments. Another advantage of MIS is that it minimizes information overload, which can be quite common with conventional businesses in the modern era.

Information systems have to be designed and managed in such way that it aggregates information, monitors the organization's activities and operations and enhances

communication and collaboration among employees. This ensures better planning for all activities and better ways to measure performance, manage resources and facilitate compliance with industry and government regulations. Control helps in forecasting, preparing accurate budgets and providing the tools and vital information to employees, top management and business partners.

2.2 COUNTRY WIDE CINEMA INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The system covers all cinemas in a country, but depending upon needs, it can integrate cinemas of other countries as well. Any cinema has one or more rooms, and each room contains a set of seats. A room can be built and integrated in the system through a room Designer interface, managed through a web based cinema manager interface. In future releases, this system will provide an interface allowing existing cinema management systems to easily adapt to communicate with the system.

People should use this system to find particular movie-sessions by various search criteria like country, area, city, time, and cinema or movie title. When entering the web-page the system automatically sets the search conditions to the local area, and a time interval spanning the rest of the current day. When the user has entered search criteria he or she will be presented with a list of session-links that fulfill the criteria or an empty list. Clicking a session link returns a graphical presentation of the room of the session, at which seats can be selected/deselected, a total prize displayed and a booking-commit button. A booking number will be displayed at the screen. The user can bring along this booking number and have the tickets printed later. Also, this

booking number is essential if the user should have his/her money back due to session-cancellation, disease or other problems. If a user does not pay before some time limit, specified by the local cinema, before the session begins, the reservation will automatically be cancelled and the corresponding set of seats becomes available for other users. When the movie has been on for some time-span, which is also set by the cinema manager, booking or buying a ticket for that particular session is no longer possible. However, the session information is kept for some time to handle any customer-requests or -complaints. Upon payment, printing the corresponding tickets is possible at any computer connected to the internet and a printer, or at any cinema covered by the system. It is the user's responsibility to take care of the tickets because a given ticket, representing a seat, can only be printed once. (Steward 2011)

The system provides functionality for a cinema manager to schedule future movies at his/her own cinema, i.e., entering sessions into the database, as well as changing the scheduling and correcting errors in scheduling.

FIG 2.1 Structure of a movie theatre seat booking system.

2.3 ONLINE MOVIE THEATRE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM

This is a online web site on which user as well as theatre owner register themselves and use this site to update movies in theatre and search for particular location of theatre as well as book tickets for particular movie. Also theatre authority can check by ticket number for valid user.

2.4 DATA BASE DESIGN STRUCTURE FOR AN INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR A MOVIE THEATER

According A local movie theater is interested in building a database information system. The database will keep the information about the customers, sales, etc. The system will enable the management to analyze the progress of the business, create financial reports, etc.

An important aspect of this project is to develop a web application that will allow the customers to check the schedule of movies and purchase tickets on-line.

fig 2.2 overall structure of a cinema management system

2.5. DATABASE DESIGN FOR A MOVIE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

We represent the main entity types of this database. For each entity type, we provide some of the corresponding attributes. Use this information in order to: (a) Build an Enhanced E-R diagram; (b) Transform the Enhanced E-R diagram to a relational database. Identify the primary key(s) and the foreign key(s) for each relation. Draw the relational integrality constraints; (c) For each of the relations created, indicate its normal form. If the relation is not in the 3NF, decompose it into 3NF relations.

1. Customer: The main attributes are identification number, name, address, telephone number, e-mail, etc.
2. Employee: The main attributes are identification number, name, address, date of hire, employment history, salary, etc.
3. Movie: The main attributes are identification number, title, year of production, awards won, description, actors, location, etc.
4. Showroom: The main attributes are location, name, capacity, etc.
5. Producer: The main attributes are identification number, name, address, contact information, current balance, etc.

Note the following: (a) Awards won and Actors are multi-value attributes of the entity type Movie. (b) Employment history is a multi-value attribute of the entity type Employee. (c) A movie is played in at least one showroom and it is played at least once a day. When a movie is assigned to a showroom, the following information is

recorded: the timetable and the total number of tickets available per show. (d) When a customer purchases tickets for a movie, the following is recorded: ticket number, date, unit price, amount paid, and number of tickets purchased. The number of tickets purchased reduces the total number of tickets available. (e) Some of the customers choose to become members in order to buy tickets on-line. For members, the following additional information is required: login name and password. (f) When the movie theater purchases movies from a producer, the following information is recorded: transaction number, purchase price, purchase date, payment due date, and amount due.

2.5.1 ACCESS APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT

The following are some of the queries, forms, and reports one can create in order to increase the functionality of the database:

Queries:

1. The following set of queries helps with financial analysis:
 - a. Create a query that presents the monthly revenues from ticket sales, the monthly expenses from salaries, the monthly expenses from purchasing new movies, and the monthly earnings.
 - b. Create a query that presents the total revenues, total expenses, and earnings during the current year.

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2. Create a query that lists the five best movies of the current year. This classification is based on the number of awards won.
 3. List the five most expensive movies of the current year.
 4. Create a query that presents the total number of tickets sold per movie. Sort the information in descending order of the total number of tickets.
 5. Create a query that presents the average capacity usage of a showroom during the current year.
 6. Create a query that lists the one hundred most preferable customers.
 7. Create a query that presents detailed information about the producer with whom the theater did the most business during the current year.
 8. Create a query that prompts for a date and returns the movie schedule for the selected date and the total number of available tickets per show.
 9. Create a query that prompts for the name of a movie and returns the weekly schedule of the selected movie and the total number of available tickets per show.
 10. Create a query that prompts for the name of a customer and returns details about the ticket purchases made by the selected customer during the current month.

2.5.2 FORM SCREENS

1. Create a user sign-in form together with a registration form for new users.

-
2. Create the following data entry forms that are used for database administrative functions: employees, movies, customers, movie timetables, etc. These forms allow the user to add, update, and delete information about employees, movies, customers, movie timetables, etc.
 3. Create a form that enables the user to browse through the financial reports created.
 4. Create a form that would enable the user to select a movie title from a combo box. Insert a subform that presents the weekly timetable of the selected movie and the total number of available tickets per show. Insert textboxes to present the following information about the selected movie: production year, name of the producer, and a description of the movie. Insert a command button that, when clicked-on, returns a list with details about the awards won by the selected movie. Insert a command button that, when clicked-on, returns details about the actors who perform in the movie. Insert a command button that allows the user to purchase a ticket. When the user clicks-on this button (a) the user sign-in form opens. If the user is not a member, the user registration form opens. (b) Next, the data entry form opens to enable the user to purchase a ticket.
 5. Create a form that allows the user to browse through the information saved in this database about actors. Insert a subform that presents details about the movies performed in by the selected actor. Insert a subform that presents details about the awards won by the selected actor.

6. Create a form that allows the user to browse through the information saved in this database about producers. Insert a subform that presents details about the movies purchased during the current year from the selected producer.

7. Create a form that allows the user to browse through the information saved in the database about customers. Insert a subform that presents details about the ticket purchases of the selected customer during the last month. Insert textboxes that present the following information: the total amount of money the selected customer has spent during the current month; the total revenues generated from ticket sales during the current month; and the total revenues from ticket sales during the current year. Insert a command button that, when clicked-on, returns details about the most preferred customers.

2.6 DATA TO BE MANAGED

An information management system generally manages data. In the case of a cinema management system, the following data would be managed.

2.6.1 MOVIES

This data would include a listing of the movies to be shown in the cinema, details of the movie such as title, cast, and introduction including a short clip perhaps. All these could be assessed on the system.

2.6.2 SEATS

The number and details of seats are registered on the system. This enables automated allocation or manual choosing by users on the system. This flexibility allows for preference in choosing a seat.

2.6.3 VIEWER DATA

The data of the viewer also needs to be managed as the viewer would provide personal details including a passport photograph.

2.7 PAYMENT SYSTEMS

Here we discuss the available payment systems which could be used in processing payments for a web based cinema information management system.

2.6.1 ELECTRONIC PAYMENT AND ONLINE ELECTRONIC PAYMENT FOR TICKETING

Jing, (2011) explained that online electronic payments are not tantamount to electronic payments. In the emergence of e-commerce, credit cards have long been represented by electronic means of payment, credit cards in shopping malls. Many hotels and other places and items could swipe of the card, POS terminals Regulations, ATM cash forms of payment. And online electronic payments, online payments also known as electronic currency, broadly speaking, refer to a transaction in the online exchange of funds; It is a network-based electronic financial, a business card transactions for all types of electronic tools and media, the electronic computer and communications technologies as a means Electronic data (binary data) stored in the bank's computer system and through the computer network system in the form of the flow of electronic information transfer and payment. Electronic Payment System is the basis for online payments, and online payments system development is a higher form of electronic payment. It makes electronic payment may, at any time, through the Internet directly to the transfer, settlement and form e-business environment.

2.6.2. USE OF SCRATCH CARDS WITH PREDEFINED PINS AND SERIAL NUMBERS

In online shopping online electronic payment function is the key issue to ensure the consumers are fast and convenient, we have to ensure the safety and secrecy of the parties to a transaction, which requires a complete electronic trading systems.

Currently, several online electronic payment systems used which include internet Bank Card Payment System Including online credit card, smart card (IC card) payment systems and are established in accordance with the standards set shopping and payment system. Thus using scratch cards which have been automatically generated and printed without patterns vulnerable to hackers presents another alternative method of paying for seats in a cinema. These scratch cards could be purchased as a regular feature like normal recharge cards. On logging on to the site, users could then fill in their personal information along side the scratch card details to get a seat reserved.

CHAPTER THREE

DESIGN ARCHITECTURE FOR WEB BASED CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In this section, we present the design of our proposed system with technical details such as flow charts, use case diagram and data base table structures. We also present an analysis of the existing system, Kathmandu plaza with the properties of the new proposed system with the aim of solving those problems discovered.

3.2 ANALYSIS OF THE EXISTING SYSTEM

The ticketing system of Kathmandu plaza is done in the cinema arena. The payments are done there in cash and choices of seats are not presented. The data of the viewer is not entered properly into the system for future references and the process is generally slow as persons have to queue up to be attended to.

3.3 PROBLEMS OF EXISTING SYSTEM

From the general flow of data in the current system, we found the following problems

- Lack of comfort- the whole seat allocation system is manual. Users are not able to book and register seats from their comfort zone. There is no provision for reserving seat by proxy. This makes the overall process slow.

-
- Deleting and adding new seats proves to be complicated as manual records need to be updated and it does not reflect on all points of contact.
 - There is no digital data of a person entering the cinema hall which could be useful for security purposes.
 - Design and printing of tickets is not fully automated but designed as a template and printed for all seats pending who takes the seat
 - Cash is paid on site which makes physical cash present in the site and this proves to be risky in crime zones.

3.4 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The web based cinema seat allocation system will have the following features

- Network access – this means it could be used either on the internet or on a local area network (LAN).
- Remote seat reservation – seats could be reserved by individuals from their homes before coming to the cinema. They also get to see the list of movies viewing on a particular day.
- Automatic management of seats – the system would have a panel for automatically generating seat numbers and id. This would also aid the adding or removal of seats.
- Printing of tickets would be automated showing the picture of the person reserving a seat.

-
- Generation of serial numbers and pins for cinema scratch cards would also be possible with option for printing. These cards would be paid for and used in reserving the seats.

3.5 ARCHITECTURE FOR PROPOSED NETWORK

In this section, we use a use case diagram to show the overall use of the system summarizing each function and process carried out by a user of the system. The main users are the customer and administrator. The roles of the customer include purchasing a scratch card, entering data online, making a seat reservation and printing out the acknowledgement slip or ticket. The role of the administrator is to register pins and serial numbers, register and manage seats and see who seats have been assigned to in case of any fraudulent acts. The figure below shows the use case diagram of the web based cinema seat allocation system.

USER

Purchase Scratch card and obtain serial number and pin

Login to the site and enter personal data, scratch card details

Chooses seat and reserves it

Prints out Ticket and presents it for verification in the cinema

ADMIN

Registers seats and pins

Deletion of expired users and monitoring of system

Seat Allocation Flow Chart

Seat Registration Flow Chart

Viewing Events Flow Chart

3.4.2 DATABASE DESIGN

The system has one master database named “cinema”. The database has tables – seats, users, pins

Table 3.1 SEAT RECORD TABLE

S/N	FIELD NAME	DATA TYPE	LENGTH
1.	ID	INT	255
2.	HALL	VARCHAR	20
3.	ROW	VARCHAR	30
4.	SEAT	VARCHAR	40
5.	OWNER	VARCHAR	40
6.	DATEENTRY	VARCHAR	4
7.	DATEEXIT	VARCHAR	10

Table 3.2 PINS TABLE

S/N	FIELD NAME	DATA TYPE	LENGTH
1.	ID	VARCHAR	255
2.	PIN	VARCHAR	50
3.	SERIAL	VARCHAR	50
4.	OWNER	VARCHAR	50
5.	USED	VARCHAR	60

TABLE 3.3 USERS TABLE

S/N	FIELD NAME	DATA TYPE	LENGTH
1.	Id	INT	255
2.	FIRSTNAME	VARCHAR	30
3.	LASTNAME	VARCHAR	30
4.	OTHERNAME	VARCHAR	30
5.	MOBILE	VARCHAR	11
6.	EMAIL	VARCHAR	20
7.	ADDRESS	VARCHAR	20
8	SEAT	VARCHAR	255

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter presents the hardware required for the cinema seat allocation System in section 4.1. The software requirement for the system is presented in section 4.2. Section 4.3 presents the implementation technique of the system.

4.1 HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT FOR THE SYSTEM

The hardware required for the development of the system is listed below

- 1) Server system – CPU – 1.4 Ghz or higher.
- 2) Storage – 1Terabyte or higher
- 3) Network cables
- 4) Routers
- 5) Internet modem
- 6) Email server

The software requirement for this software are

- 1) Client side operating system like win xp, 7 , 8 etc
- 2) Server side operating system like linux, windows server 2008 r2 etc
- 3) Web browser

4.2 CHOICE OF PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE - PHP

Shafik & Ramsey (2006), defined PHP as a server-side scripting language designed for web development but also used as a general-purpose programming language. PHP is now installed on more than 20 million websites and 1 million web servers. Originally created by Rasmus Lerdorf in 1995, the reference implementation of PHP is now produced by The PHP Group. While PHP originally stood for Personal Home Page, it is now said to stand for PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor, a recursive acronym. PHP code is interpreted by a web server with a PHP processor module which generates the resulting web page: PHP commands can be embedded directly into an HTML source document rather than calling an external file to process data. It has also evolved to include a command-line interface capability and can be used in standalone graphical applications. PHP is free software released under the PHP License, which is incompatible with the GNU General Public License (GPL) due to restrictions on the usage of the term PHP. PHP can be deployed on most web servers and also as a standalone shell on almost every operating system and platform, free of charge.

On May 22, 2000, PHP 4, powered by the Zend Engine 1.0, was released. As of August 2008 this branch is up to version 4.4.9. PHP 4 is no longer under development nor will any security updates be released.

On July 13, 2004, PHP 5 was released, powered by the new Zend Engine II. PHP 5 included new features such as improved support for object-oriented programming, the PHP Data Objects (PDO) extension (which defines a lightweight and consistent

interface for accessing databases), and numerous performance enhancements. In 2008 PHP 5 became the only stable version under development. Late static binding had been missing from PHP and was added in version 5.3.

A new major version has been under development alongside PHP 5 for several years. This version was originally planned to be released as PHP 6 as a result of its significant changes, which included plans for full Unicode support. However, Unicode support took developers much longer to implement than originally thought, and the decision was made in March 2010 to move the project to a branch, with features still under development moved to trunk.

PHP was used in the development of this project for the following reasons

1. PHP is an open source programming language and it is free. It also ensures flexibility – this means that the program could be hosted online on a network – internet or intranet or offline on a single computer
2. PHP is user friendly like simple and easy to learn compare to other programming languages like C, C++, and ASP.net.
3. PHP can be easily integrates into HTML, even you can manage it without using HTML as well.
4. PHP is cross platform support language and it can be supported on most web servers and runs on all major operating systems like Linux, Mac OS PHP can be used

to develop web applications for personal websites to e-commerce applications and community portals sites e.g. discussion forums, blogs etc.

5. PHP doesn't use a lot of the system's resources so it runs fast and doesn't tend to slow other processes down. It is typically used as an Apache module, written in C, so it loads and executes quickly. It works well with other software and can be quite fast. PHP is also fairly stable and since it is open source, the PHP community works together to fix any bugs. The community offers technical support and continuously updates the code further expanding PHP's capabilities.

6. Another key advantage of PHP is its connective abilities. PHP uses a modular system of extensions to interface with a variety of libraries such as graphics, XML, encryption, etc. In addition, programmers can extend PHP by writing their own extensions and compiling them into the executable or they can create their own executable and load it using PHP's dynamic loading mechanism.

4.3 IMPLEMENTATION TECHNIQUE

The software is in form of a website so it has to be installed on a server in the network and accessed over the network by client systems which in this case would be used by clients on their web browsers

4.3.1 SETTING UP THE SOFTWARE (LOCAL AREA NETWORK)

- Install apache2triad.5.4.exe
- Use “password” as the password
- At the end of the installation enter the password again when asked
- The screen will not show the password
- Restart system
- Copy the folder “cinema” to c:\apache2triad\htdocs\
- Open “localhost/phpmyadmin/” from web browser enter: root and password
- Click import and select the file “ database.sql” from the cinema folder
- And click go.
- Run the program with http://localhost/cinema from web browser

4.3.2 SETTING UP THE SOFTWARE (WEBSITE IMPLEMENTATION)

- Purchase a domain name www.Kathmanducinema.com
- Pay for the hosting
- Get the username and password for the cpanel from hosting provider
- Login to the cpanel using www.Kathmanducinema.com/cpanel

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- Locate the file uploader and upload all the files in the cinema folder into the www folder on the site
 - Open the phpmyadmin panel and create a new database
 - Import the database file database.sql using the browse/choose button to get it into the phpmyadmin
 - Verify that the connect.php password and username are set to the new credentials provided for your hosting.
 - Logout and run the set from the webbrowser using the website www.Kathmanducinema.com

4.3.3 USING THE SOFTWARE

- Run the program with <http://localhost/cinema> or www.Kathmanducinema.com from web browser
- Login with user credentials provided by administrator
- Exit the site when done.

4.4 SYSTEM TESTING

The system was tested using 5 persons. The data of these persons were collected and five scratch cards were printed out. Each of the person's details were entered into the system including passports and the scratch card details were also entered.

4.4.1 OUTPUT

The result showed that 5 seats chosen by the persons were allocated and the seats differed because once a seat has been taken, it is locked to the user till 24 hours. The mobile no of the persons served as a key to reprinting or accessing the ticket data.

4.4.2 ERROR CHECK

To test for errors, the system was subjected to fake scratch cards which proved invalid. Persons registered attempted registration with the same mobile number. This directed the person to his seat details.

4.5 SYSTEM MAINTENANCE

The system would be maintained in the following ways

- Renewal of internet hosting fee – this requires a payment to the internet hosting company for a period of one year interval.
- The administrator would check for seats that are invalid from time to time to remove them from the allocation list
- The administrator would generate scratch cards for the number of seats present for the daily cinema views.
- The administrator would delete expired users from the system.

CHAPTER FIVE – SUMMARY CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.0 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This project focused on the design and implementation of an online Cinema Information Management System for the management of seat information in Kathmandu plaza. The system was developed to carry out the functions of managing cinema seat information, user information and scratch card pin and serial generation. The system would greatly enhance the allocation of seats and online access to seat and movie information from the comforts of the home.

5.1 RECOMMENDATION

It is hereby recommended for this system to be adopted for use by Kathmandu plaza and other cinema viewing centers.

REFERENCES

- Acharya, Kamal. "STUDENT INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM." *Authorea Preprints* (2023).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Library Management System." Available at SSRN4807104 (2019).
- ACHARYA, KAMAL, et al. "LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM." (2019).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Online bus reservation system project report." *Authorea Preprints* (2024).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Online bus reservation system project report." (2024).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Online Bus Reservation System." *SSRN ElectroNIC ASIA Journal* (2024): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal. "Student Information Management System Project." *SSRN ElectroNIC ASIA Journal* (2024): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal. "ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM." *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science* (2023): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal. "College Information Management System." *SSRN ElectroNIC ASIA Journal* (2024): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal, Attendance Management System Project (April 28, 2024). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
- Acharya, Kamal, Online Food Order System (May 2, 2024). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
- Acharya, Kamal, University management system project. (May 1, 2024). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
- Acharya, Kamal, Online banking management system. (May 1, 2024). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
- Acharya, Kamal, Online Job Portal Management System (May 5, 2024). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
- Acharya, Kamal, Employee leave management system. (May 7, 2024). Available
at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>

Acharya, Kamal, Online electricity billing project report. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>

Acharya, Kamal, POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>

Acharya, Kamal, Online job placement system project report. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>

Acharya, Kamal, Software testing for project report. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>

Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>

Acharya, Kamal, Burber ordering system project report. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>

Acharya, Kamal, Teachers Record Management System Project Report (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>

Acharya, Kamal, Dairy Management System Project Report (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>

Acharya, Kamal, Electrical Shop Management System Project (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>

Acharya, Kamal, Online book store management system project report. (February 10, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>

Acharya, Kamal, Paint shop management system project report. (January 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>

Acharya, Kamal, Supermarket billing system project report. (August 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>

Acharya, Kamal, Online taxi booking system project report. (March 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>

Acharya, Kamal, Online car servicing system project report. (March 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>

Acharya, Kamal, School management system project report. (July 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>

Acharya, Kamal, Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report (March 21, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>

Acharya, Kamal, Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report (March 21, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>

Home Page

Book a seat

Movies

CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
USEN POLYTECHNIC

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10. *The Hobbit: The Desolation of Smaug*

Warner Bros.
Who could guess, after the meandering first feature in a seemingly unnecessary eight-hour trilogy of films based on a novel of less than 300 pages, that Peter Jackson had such a vigorous and thrilling middle episode in store? With Bilbo (Martin Freeman), Gandalf (Ian McKellen) and the diverse fealty

Reprint –

CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
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Enter Mobile Number to Ticket

Mobile Number :

Web Master
 Admin

Cinema Management Software
This Web based software helps to manage cinema films in stock and costs of seats for viewing, it automates seat allocation and price computation.

Designed By
 [Usen Polytechnic](#)
Computer Science Student

Project © 2013-2014

Admin panel

Seat Registration

Hall Name	<input type="text"/>	
Row/Section	<input type="text"/>	
Seat No	<input type="text"/>	
TO	<input type="text"/>	
<input type="button" value="Generate"/>		

S/NO:	Hall	Row	Seat	Owner	Operation	
1	Screen D	First	1		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
2	Screen D	First	2	07036307980	X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
3	Screen D	First	3		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
4	Screen D	First	4		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
5	Screen D	First	5		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
6	Screen D	First	6	05025232654	X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
7	Screen D	First	7		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
8	Screen D	First	8		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
9	Screen D	First	9		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
10	Screen D	First	10		X	<input type="button" value="✕"/>

Page

Appendix B: Code Listing

```
<?PHP include ('head.php');?>
```

```
<section id="content">
```

```
<div class="main">
```

```
<div class="slider-wrapper">
```

```
<div class="slider">
```

```

```

```
<ul class="items">
```

<strong class="banner">

x

View

View Movies

<b class="margin-bot">Take a look at the movies to be viewed with dates

VIEW

<strong class="banner">

x

Book

a Seat

<b class="margin-bot">Book a seat before running down to the cinema

Book Now

</div>

<ul class="pagination">

</div>

<div class="border-bot1 img-indent-bot">

<h2>Cinema Information Management System </h2>

</div>

<div class="wrapper">

<article class="col-1">

<div class="indent-left">

<ul class="list-1">

THE HOBBIT: THE DESOLATION OF SMAUG

Director: Peter Jackson

Cast: Martin Freeman, Richard Armitage, Orlando Bloom, Benedict Cumberbatch,

Evangeline Lily, Luke Evans

Date Viewing: 14-01-2014

</div>

</article>

```
<article class="col-2">
```

```
<h3><a href="#"><strong>THOR - THE DARK WORLD</strong></a></h3>
```

```
<h3>-<span class="p1"><a href="http://blog.templatemonster.com/2011/10/31/free-  
website-template-slider-design-studio/">DATE VIEWING - 14-02-2014
```

```
</a></span></h3>
```

```
<div class="p1">
```

```
<figure class="img-border"></figure>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</article>
```

```
<article class="col-3">
```

```
<div class="indent-top">
```

```
<ul class="list-2">
```

```
<ul>
```

```
<li><a class="item" href="#">Our CENTERES </a>
```

```
<span>Kathmandu Plaza, Sapele Rd, benin City </span>
```

```
</li>
```

<li class="last-item">Entertainment

Car Race, Fast Food, Games and More...

</div>

</article>

</div>

</div>

</section>

<?php include ('footer.php');?>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="en">

<head>

<title></title>

<meta charset="utf-8">

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/reset.css" type="text/css"
media="screen">

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css" type="text/css"
media="screen">

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/layout.css" type="text/css"
media="screen">

<script src="js/jquery-1.6.3.min.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="js/cufon-yui.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="js/cufon-replace.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="js/NewsGoth_400.font.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="js/NewsGoth_700.font.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="js/Vegur_300.font.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

```
<script src="js/FF-cash.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
```

```
<script type="text/javascript"
src="js/jquery.googlemaps1.01.js"></script>
```

```
<script type="text/javascript">
```

```
$(function() {
```

```
    /* For zebra striping */
```

```
    $("table tr:nth-child(odd)").addClass("odd-row");
```

```
    /* For cell text alignment */
```

```
    $("table td:first-child, table th:first-child").addClass("first");
```

```
    /* For removing the last border */
```

```
    $("table td:last-child, table th:last-child").addClass("last");
```

```
});
```

```
</script>
```

```
<!--[if lt IE 7]>
```

```
<div style=' clear: both; text-align:center; position: relative;'>
```

```
<a href="http://windows.microsoft.com/en-US/internet-explorer/products/ie/home?ocid=ie6_countdown_bannercode">
```

```

```

```
</a>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<![endif-->
```

```
<!--[if lt IE 9]>
```

```
<script type="text/javascript" src="js/html5.js"></script>
```

```
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/ie.css" type="text/css"  
media="screen">
```

```
<![endif-->
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body id="page5">
```

<!--

=====header=====

=====-->

<header>

<div class="main">

<div class="wrapper">

<h1>

DesignStudio

USEN POLYTECHNIC

</h1>

<nav>

<ul class="menu">

Home

Book

Seat

```
</li><a
href="movies.php">Movies</a></li>
```

```
</li><a href="reprint.php">Re-
Print </a></li>
```

```
</li><a
href="contact.php">Contact </a></li>
```

```
</ul>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</header>
```

```
<section id="content">
```

```
<div class="main">
```

```
<div class="indent-left">
```

```
<div class="wrapper">
```

```
<?php session_start();?>
```

```
<?php
```

```
include ('connect.php');
```

```
if (isset($_POST['regstudent']))
```

```
{
```

```
if (empty($_POST['mobile']) or empty($_POST['surname']) or  
empty($_POST['firstname']) )
```

```
{ $regerror = "Fill All Details"; include('register.php'); exit; }
```

```
$mobile = $_POST['mobile'];
```

```
$qry = mysql_query("select * from seats where owner = ('$mobile') and assigned =  
'yes' ") or die(mysql_error());
```

```
$noH = mysql_num_rows($qry);
```

```
$datax = mysql_fetch_array($qry);
```

```
if ($noH > 0)
```

```
{
```

```
$regerror = '['.$datax['hall']. ' ' .$datax['row']. ' row - seat '.$datax['number'].'] Already
```

```
Allocated to ('$mobile.');
```

```
include ('register.php');
```

```
exit;
```

```
}
```

```
//fix seat

$gender = $_POST['gender'];

$qry = mysql_query("select * from seats where assigned = 'no' ") or
die(mysql_error());

$noH = mysql_num_rows($qry);

$selectB = '<select name="choice">';

for ($i=1;$i<=$noH;$i++)

{

$dataB = mysql_fetch_array($qry);

$selectB .= '<option value="'. $dataB['id']. "' >

'.$dataB['hall'].-'.$dataB['row'].'-row-seat-'.$dataB['number'].</option>';

}

$selectB .= '</select>';
```

```
if ($noH == 0)
```

```
{
```

```
$regerror = 'Seat Spaces Exhausted for this Category ('. $gender .)';
```

```
include ('register.php');
```

```
exit;
```

```
}
```

```
$_SESSION['mobile'] = $_POST['mobile'];
```

```
$_SESSION['gender'] = $_POST['gender'];
```

```
$dateenter = date('Y-m-d');
```

```
$dateexit = date('Y-m-d', strtotime('+1 days')); //one year from now
```

```
//uploading passport
```

```
if ($_FILES['passport']['name']!="")
```

```
{
```

```
$passportname = $_FILES['passport']['name'];
```

```
$array = explode('.', $passportname);
```

```
$extension = $array[1];
```

```
$passportname = $_POST['mobile'].'.'.$extension;
```

```
if ($_FILES['passport']['size']>90000){$regerror = "Passport too Large!";  
include('register.php'); exit; }
```

```
//upload passport...
```

```
move_uploaded_file($_FILES['passport']['tmp_name'], "passports/" . $_POST['mobile'] .  
'.' . $extension);
```

```
}
```

```
else //if no passport uploaded
```

```
{ $passportname = 'nil'; }
```

```
mysql_query("insert into users (firstname,surname,dob,gender,email,mobile,address,
dateenter,dateexit,passport)

values (

'{{$POST['firstname']}}',

'{{$POST['surname']}}',

'{{$POST['dob']}}',

'{{$POST['gender']}}',

'{{$POST['email']}}',

'{{$POST['mobile']}}',

'{{$POST['address']}}',

'{$dateenter}',

'{$dateexit}',

'{$passportname}'

)")

or die (mysql_error());
```

}

?>

<?php include ('head.php');?>

<div align="center">

<form method="post" id="contact-form" action="print.php?regserial=set">

<p><?php echo ''. \$error. '';?> </p>

<p> Fill in Details of Cinema Card Serial Number and Pin

</p>

<p>

Choose Seat

<?php echo \$selectB;?>

</p>

<p>Serial No: <input name="serial" placeholder="Enter Serial No of Card"
type="text" class="text" />

</p>

<p> Pin:<input name="pin" placeholder="Enter PIN" type="text" class="text" />

</p><div class="6u">

<input type="submit" class="button" name="regserial" value="Finish">

</div>

</form>

</div>

<?php include ('footer.php');?>

```
<?php include ('head.php');?>
```

```
<form id="contact-form" method="post" action="serial.php"
enctype="multipart/form-data">
```

```
<div align="center">
```

```
<p>
```

```
<style>
```

```
div {
```

```
padding:15px;
```

```
margin:0;
```

```
}
```

```
</style>
```

```
<span style="font-weight: bold"> Purchase a cinema scratch card for N1000 per seat
from any outlet.</span></p>
```

```
<p style="font-weight: bold">Fill in your Personal Details to proceed with the
registration </p>
```

```
<p><span><font color="#CC3300"><?php echo $regerror;?></font></span></p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div style="width:60%">
```

```
<div align="" style="">
```

```
<div>
```

```
<fieldset><legend>Personal Details</legend>
```

```
<p style="font-weight: bold">*Surname <input name="surname" style="float:right"
placeholder="Surname" value="<?php echo $_POST['surname'];?>" type="text"
class="text" />
```

```
</p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div>
```

```
<p><span style="font-weight: bold">*First</span> <span style="font-weight:
bold">Name</span><input name="firstname" value="<?php echo
$_POST['firstname'];?>" style="float:right" placeholder="First Name" type="text"
class="text" />
```

```
</p>
```

</div>

<div>

<p style="font-weight: bold">Gender <select style="float:right" name="gender">

<option value="M">M</option>

<option value="F">F</option>

</select>

</p>

</div>

</fieldset>

</div>

<div>

<fieldset>

<legend></legend>

<div>

<p style="font-weight: bold">Address</p>

<p style="font-weight: bold"><textarea name="address"></textarea></p>

<p style="font-weight: bold">Email</p>

<p style="font-weight: bold"><input name="email" type="email"></p>

</div>

<div>

<p style="font-weight: bold">Mobile</p>

</div>

<div>

<p style="font-weight: bold"><input type="text" name="mobile"></p>

</div></fieldset>

<div>

<fieldset><legend>Upload Passport</legend>

<p>

<input type="file" style="float:left;" name="passport" />

[*jpeg/*jpg/*.png]</p>

```
</fieldset></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div></div>
```

```
<input type="submit" style="float:left" class="button" name="regstudent"
```

```
value="Next">>>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<p>&nbsp;</p>
```

```
<p>&nbsp;</p>
```

```
<p><br>
```

```
</p>
```

```
<p>&nbsp;</p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</form>
```

```
<?php include ('footer.php');?>
```